

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

LATIN AMERICA BIOIMAGING (LABI)

A Collaborative Network to Advance Bioimaging in Latin America

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

What is LABI?

Latin America Bioimaging (LABI) is a collaborative network interested in addressing bioimaging needs such as training, education, and open access to imaging technologies across the Latin American and Caribbean regions

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

What is LABI?

Latin America Bioimaging (LABI) is a collaborative network interested in addressing bioimaging needs such as training, education, and accessibility to imaging technologies across the Latin American and Caribbean regions

**Bring together Imaging scientists,
tecnicians, technology developers
& companies**

**Coordinate to foster community
and capacity building**

**Promote integration to the
international community**

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

How is the network progressing?

How are we going to establish as a reference network?

LABI Steering Committee

Outgoing-Chair

Andrés Kamaid

(Institut Pasteur de Montevideo)

Chair

Lía Pietrasanta

(Universidad de Buenos Aires)

Alternate-Chair

Kildare Miranda

(Universidade Federal do Rio
de Janeiro)

Network Manager

Andres Olivera

"oliver"

- **Hernandes Carvalho** (Universidade Estadual de Campinas)
- **Steffen Hartel** (Universidad de Chile)
- **Verónica Eisner** (Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile)
- **Iván Rey** (Universidad de los Andes)
- **Juan Orozco** (**Universidad de los Andes**)
- **Christopher Wood** (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México)
- **Iskra Tuero** (Universidad Peruana Cayetano Heredia)
- **Leonel Malacrida** (Institut Pasteur, Universidad de la República)
- **Gabriela Casanova** (Universidad de la República)
- **Andrés Romero-Carvajal** (Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador)

Latin America
Bioimaging

Community members

2022

Members per Country

- 137** Total Members
- 123** Living in LatAm
- 19** Total Countries
- 11** LatAm Countries

Community members

2022

- 137** Total Members
- 123** Living in LatAm
- 19** Total Countries
- 11** LatAm Countries

Members per Country

Created with Datawrapper

2023

- 297** Total Members
- 266** Living in LatAm
- 23** Total Countries
- 13** LatAm Countries

Community members

2023

Members per Country

297 Total Members
266 Living in LatAm
23 Total Countries
13 LatAm Countries

Created with Datawrapper

2024

626 Total Members
569 Living in LatAm
33 Total Countries
15 LatAm Countries

Strengthening Community Governance in Latin American Bioimaging Network

The project aims to implement community governance in LABI, promoting:

- **Openness**
- **Transparency**
- **Accountability.**

197 Applications
51 Countries

8 Funded Projects

In collaboration

What we do?

BUILDING COMMUNITY

**Providing a centralized and updated
platform of opportunities and resources**

Organizing annual meetings
and Satellite events

BUILDING CAPACITIES

Supporting training and career
development programs

PROMOTING GLOBAL INTEGRATION

Promoting the regional and
global integration

Addressing regional needs through
collaboration in working groups

Powered by **MicroscopyDB**

- Event, Courses and Workshops
- Job opportunities
- Training Resources
- **Core facilities Map**

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

Building Momentum through Community Engagement

The screenshot shows the website's navigation menu with 'CORE FACILITIES' highlighted. The main content area features a map of Latin America and the Caribbean with purple location pins. The left sidebar contains the following text:

DESCRIPTION
Developmental Biology laboratory equipped with optical and fluorescence microscopes. Provides training in research and bioimaging to undergraduate and master's students.

TECHNIQUES/EQUIPMENT
Optical microscopy, Fluorescence microscopy

Anisotropy/Polarization Microscopy | Light Microscopy | Functional Imaging and specialized methodologies, Feedback Microscopy | Light Microscopy | Functional Imaging and specialized methodologies, in vivo optical imaging | Animal & Plant Imaging, Tissue Clearing | Light Microscopy | Functional Imaging and specialized methodologies

WHO CAN USED IT?
Open within Institution/University users,
Open by appointment

CONTACT
Andrés Romero-Carvajal
maromero@uce.edu.ec

76

Core Facilities

11

Countries

15.000

**VIEWS/
3 YEAR**

**Register your
Facility/Lab**

Latin America
Bioimaging

labi.lat

Powered by **MicroscopyDB**

- Event, Courses and Workshops
- Job opportunities
- Training Resources
- **Core facilities Map**

Next steps

- Coordinate & standardize regional Infrastructure
- Provide a virtual Hub
 - Cloud storage
 - Computing

Building Momentum through Community Engagement

2022

2023

2024

FOLLOWERS

292

871

1221

SUSCRIBERS
VIEWS

26

42

72

485

928

4.0 K

FOLLOWERS

LAUNCHED
61

610

3 Months (May- July)
VIEWS

NEW USERS

1.1 K

5.6 K

620

1.7 K

What we do?

BUILDING COMMUNITY

Providing a centralized and updated platform of opportunities and resources

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

BUILDING CAPACITIES

Supporting training and career development programs

PROMOTING GLOBAL INTEGRATION

Promoting the regional and global integration

Addressing regional needs through collaboration in working groups

LABI Training & Career Development Programs

63 TRAVEL SUPPORTS FOR THE
NEXT THREE YEARS

2 CALLS PER YEAR

- 1** Attend Bioimaging courses (users and researchers)
- 2** Attend Bioimaging courses (staff of bioimaging service units)
- 3** Professional development and connection of Imaging Facilities in Latin America (visit or On-site training)

LABI Training & Career Development Programs

63 TRAVEL SUPPORTS FOR THE NEXT THREE YEARS

2 CALLS PER YEAR

What is covered?

- Transportation, registration, and lodging expenses.
- Up to a maximum of \$1625 USD.

What is taken into account in the evaluation?

- Professional Background
- Motivation and Personal Impact
- Community Impact

LABI Training & Career Development Programs

1st Call 2023

6 GRANTEES

2nd Call 2023

8 GRANTEES SELECTED

38 IMAGING SCIENCE FELLOWS

8 COUNTRIES

1st Call 2024

11 GRANTEES

2nd Call 2024

14 GRANTEES

Latin America
Bioimaging

Building Momentum through Community Engagement

73 Core Facilities

11 Countries

25% Involved in
Training Programs

Latin America
Bioimaging

Celina Terán

Instituto de Biotecnología,
UNAM, México

PROGRAM 1 BIOIMAGING COURSES (USERS AND RESEARCHERS)

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

Study visit

Annual Workshop in Advanced Microscopy and Biophotonics

**Advanced Bioimaging Unit,
Institut Pasteur de Montevideo**

Latin America
Bioimaging

Expected application

I will seek to apply the knowledge of the Expansion Microscopy technique acquired in the course I attended.

I aim to implement the technique in the laboratory so that different colleagues in the lab and across the country can have access to it.

Back to the Lab!

I will seek to apply the knowledge of the Expansion Microscopy technique acquired in the course I attended.

ExM Implementation in LNMA

I aim to implement the technique in the laboratory so that different colleagues in the lab and across the country can have access to it.

Latin America
Bioimaging

Isaura Suarez

Grupo de Neurociencias de Antioquia,
Universidad de Antioquia, Colombia

PROGRAM 2 BIOIMAGING COURSES (STAFF OF BIOIMAGING SERVICE UNITS)

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

Red de Equipamiento Científico
Avanzado, Universidad de Chile

This opportunity has allowed me to establish connections between laboratories and plan future Colombia-Chile collaborations.

I have compared and complemented my protocols for immunolabeling and microscopic acquisition of fluorescence, which is one of the pillars of the facility at the Institute of Biology of the University of Antioquia.

Latin America
Bioimaging

Virginia Albarracin

Centro Integral de Microscopia
Electrónica CONICET-UNT, Argentina

PROGRAMA 3 PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND CONNECTION OF
IMAGING FACILITIES IN LATIN AMERICA

Latin America Bioimaging

This experience has provided me with invaluable insights into the operation and management of a central facility, as well as exposure to state-of-the-art techniques and equipment, with applications in both life sciences and materials sciences.

1st Call 2023

2nd Call 2023

1st Call 2024

Latin America
Bioimaging

It is worth waiting for!

What we do?

BUILDING COMMUNITY

Providing a centralized and updated platform of opportunities and resources

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

BUILDING CAPACITIES

Supporting training and career development programs

PROMOTING GLOBAL INTEGRATION

Promoting the regional and global integration

Addressing regional needs through collaboration in working groups

Central hub to integrate regional initiatives

Training & Education

Developing comprehensive training programs to equip scientists with the skills needed to use and develop advanced imaging technologies.

Outreach & Integration

Engaging Communities to inspire the next generation of scientists.
Connecting our community to address microscopy accessibility

Data Science for Bioimaging

Promoting research and development in image data science, facilitating training and knowledge exchange.

WG - Outreach & Integration

Mariana De Niz

Hernán Grecco

Lyciel Paulas

Lyciel Paulas

- **Outreach for Open Science:** Engaging Communities to inspire the next generation of scientists
- **Global Dissemination:** Showcasing Latin American Science to Global Audience
- **Integration for Innovation:** Connecting Latin Americans “at home” and abroad to address microscopy accessibility gaps

WG - Outreach & Integration

Mariana De Niz

Hernán Grecco

Lyciel Paulas

- **Outreach for Open Science:** Engaging Communities to inspire the next generation of scientists

Todos los martes de Noviembre

CICLO SEMINARIOS “CIENCIA EN CONEXIÓN

Latin America Bioimaging

Scan to Register

CICLO DE SEMINARIOS

Ciencia en Conexión

El grupo de trabajo Outreach & Integration los invita a su primera sesión
Lecciones Aprendidas: Organizando Eventos Científicos con Público no Científico

Organizadores de eventos de divulgación científica a comunidades no vinculadas a la ciencia, abordan los desafíos y éxitos en la interacción con estas audiencias.

Nota: Este seminario web se presentará en español a través de Zoom.

5 Nov, 2024
12:00 - 13:00
CT / UTC-5

Speakers: Haydee Hernandez (Laboratorio Nacional de Microscopia Avanzada, UNAM, México) and Diego Delgado (Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada, México).

El grupo de trabajo Outreach & Integration los invita a su primera sesión
Superando Obstáculos: Manejo de Crisis en Eventos Presenciales

Historias de cómo los organizadores han enfrentado y resuelto problemas inesperados, desde problemas técnicos hasta cambios de última hora.

Nota: Este seminario web se presentará en español a través de Zoom.

12 Nov, 2024
12:00 - 13:00
CT / UTC-5

Speakers: Jorge Toledo (Red de Equipamiento Científico Avanzado, Universidad de Chile, Chile) and Hernán Grecco (Instituto de Física, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina).

El grupo de trabajo Outreach & Integration los invita a su primera sesión
Impacto a Largo Plazo: Cómo Crear Eventos que Resuenen

Experiencias que no solo lograron atraer público, sino que también generaron un impacto duradero en la comunidad, fomentando el interés en la ciencia.

Nota: Este seminario web se presentará en español a través de Zoom.

19 Nov, 2024
12:00 - 13:00
CT / UTC-5

Speakers: Lyciel Paulas (Microscopia Para Todos, Bolivia) and Virginia Albarracín (Centro Integral de Microscopía Electrónica, CONICET - Universidad Nacional de Tucumán, Argentina).

El grupo de trabajo Outreach & Integration los invita a su primera sesión
Innovación en Divulgación: Nuevas Formas de Involucrar al Público

Experiencias innovadoras en la organización de eventos, como el uso de tecnología, formatos no tradicionales para captar la atención del público.

Nota: Este seminario web se presentará en español a través de Zoom.

26 Nov, 2024
12:00 - 13:00
CT / UTC-5

Speakers: Federico Lecumbergy (Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de la República, Uruguay) and Federico Brown Almeida (Departamento de Zoología, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil).

WG - Training & Education

Andrés Rossi

Unidad de Microscopía,
Instituto Leloir, Argentina

Marcela Díaz

Unidad de Bioimagenología
Avanzada, IPMon, Uruguay

Victoria Repetto

Centro de Microscopía
Weber, UBA, Argentina

Ivan Rey

MicroCore, Universidad de
los Andes, Colombia

Register your
Course/Workshop

39 ACTIVITIES

7 COUNTRIES

Workshops

Courses

MAPPING BIOIMAGING TRAINING AND EDUCATION PROGRAMS IN LATIN AMERICA

Join us in identifying the programs and initiatives driving Bioimaging education across Latin America. Your participation is crucial to amplify the impact of our community

Let's work together to enhance the future of Bioimaging in Latin America!

Visit our website for more information and be part of this exciting initiative!

labi.lat

WG - Training & Education

Andrés Rossi

Unidad de Microscopía,
Instituto Leloir, Argentina

Marcela Diaz

Unidad de Bioimagenología
Avanzada, IPMon, Uruguay

Victoria Repetto

Centro de Microscopía
Weber, UBA, Argentina

Leonel Malacrida
UBA IPMon, Uruguay

Lía Pietrasanta
UMA, UBA, Argentina

Claire Brown
ABIF, McGill, Canada

Andres Olivera
LABI

**Latin American
Light Microscopy
TRAIN THE TRAINER**

3-7 JUNE, 2024

BUENOS AIRES, ARGENTINA
INSTITUTO LELOIR &
FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS EXACTAS Y NATURALES, UBA

Organized by

labi.lat | **Deadline: March 19**

24 PARTICIPANTS

8 COUNTRIES

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

Fostering Collaboration & Capacities Through Training Initiatives

WG - Data Science for Bioimaging

Coordinators

Adán Guerrero
LNMA, México

Federico Lecumberry
Facultad de Medicina,
Uruguay

Paúl Hernandez
Universidad Autónoma de
San Luis Potosí, México

The Catalyst Project LABI Hub Leader

- Develop Regional Training Programs in Image Data Science
- Enhance Access to Infrastructure and Computational Resources
- Promote Standards for Image Data Management, Analysis, and Reproducibility
- Advocate for Funding and Collaboration

Central hub to integrate regional initiatives

Training & Education

Developing comprehensive training programs to equip scientists with the skills needed to use and develop advanced imaging technologies.

Technology Developers

Bringing together developers of easy-to-disseminate hardware, software, and imaging probes to advance technology innovation

Outreach & Integration

Engaging Communities to inspire the next generation of scientists. Connecting our community to address microscopy accessibility gaps

Data & informatics

Providing a reliable and sustainable open source cloud computing and storage infrastructure

Policy & Advocacy

Advocating for policies that support equitable access to bioimaging technology and funding for research initiatives

Industry Partners

Collaborating with industry partners to facilitate technology transfer and commercialization efforts

What we do?

BUILDING COMMUNITY

Providing a centralized and updated platform of opportunities and resources

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

BUILDING CAPACITIES

Supporting training and career development programs

PROMOTING GLOBAL INTEGRATION

Promoting the regional and global integration

Addressing regional needs through collaboration in working groups

Activity Calendar 2024

Promoting global integration

SIMBIO 2024

**Simposio en
Microscopía y
Bioimágenes**

**4-5
Abr**

**25
Abr**

**COMMUNITY
EVENT
Advancing
Careers in
Bioimaging**

**Microscopy
Technology
Dissemination to
Underserved
Communities**

Janelia, Virginia, USA

**5-8
May**

**18
May**

**WORKSHOP
Community
Activity pre-
SAMIC 2024**

72 NEW MEMBERS BETWEEN ABRIL-MAY

Promote global integration

Establishing strategic partnerships

- Bioimaging network
 - Global Bioimaging (GBI)*
 - Bioimaging North America (BINA)
 - African Bioimaging Consortium (ABIC)
 - Euro Bioimaging
- Regional networks
 - Centro de Biología Estructural del Mercosur (CEBEM)*
 - Federation of Latin American and Caribbean Neuroscience Societies (FALAN)*
 - MetaDocencia

Collaborating on Projects

- MicroscopyDB *
- RI-Hubs EU_CELAC project
- The Catalyst Project *Commitment *

*MOU signed

What we do?

BUILDING COMMUNITY

Providing a centralized and updated platform of opportunities and resources

**Organizing annual meetings
and Satellite events**

BUILDING CAPACITIES

Supporting training and career development programs

PROMOTING GLOBAL INTEGRATION

Promoting the regional and global integration

Addressing regional needs through collaboration in working groups

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

2022

Virtual

44 Participants

14 Countries

1 Sponsor

In person

51 Participants

11 Countries

Exchange of Experience VII
**IMAGING IMPACT &
SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT GOALS**

Montevideo, Uruguay (Hybrid meeting)
September 14-16th, 2022

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

2022

Virtual		In person	
44	Registrants	51	Participants
14	Countries	11	Countries
1	Sponsor		

2023

Virtual		In person	
73	registrants	87	Participants
14	Countries	10	Countries
9	Sponsors		

**Latin America
Bioimaging**

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

2022

Virtual

In person

44 Registrants

51 Participants

14 Countries

11 Countries

1 Sponsor

2023

Virtual

In person

73 registrants

87 Participants

14 Countries

10 Countries

9 Sponsors

2024

Virtual

In person

82 registrants

109 Participants

14 Countries

15 Countries

10 Sponsors

3 Grants

Organizing annual meetings and Satellite events

TRAVEL GRANTS!!
LABI Meeting 2024
Deadline: May 27th
[#LABIxSuperres2024](#)

65 Aplicaciones

10 Paises

LABIxSuperres 2024 & Satellite Events

In person

40 Participants

In person

215 Participants

Virtual

82 Registrants

In person

40 Participants

Virtual

+ 100 Registrants

LABI Meeting 2024 Take Aways

We need to address strategies in Latin America

- **To train the next generation of imaging scientists**
- **To coordinate and standardize the regional bioimaging infrastructures**
- **To accelerate the development and access of innovative technologies**
 - Bringing imaging scientists closer to scientific communities
 - Disseminate technology that can be adopted
 - Promote innovation and development of new technology
 - **Enable new discoveries through bioimaging**

LABI Meeting 2025

Nov 9th - 12th, Buenos Aires, Argentina

How can you get involved?

Actively participate

 labi.lat

Join

Contact us

 latambioimaging@gmail.com

Follow Us

 [/latambioimaging/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/latambioimaging/)

 [@LatamBioimaging](https://twitter.com/LatamBioimaging)

 [latambioimaging](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC...)

